

Role of Random Texture Scattering on the Absorptance Enhancement in Halide Perovskite Layers

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid perovskites are a class of thin-film semiconductors with remarkably steep absorption edge and high absorption coefficient. In the case of solar cells, a film thickness of less than a micrometer is usually sufficient to absorb most of the light when combined with a back reflector. Otherwise, an efficient light trapping strategy may be desired, e.g. in the case of tandem or semitransparent cells. Traditionally, light trapping is accomplished by employing randomly nanotextured substrates. In this contribution, absorption enhancements due to nano-rough but also micro-rough substrates with or without additional gold coating are evaluated from the point of gains in photocurrent and from the point of view of valid optical models. We find that light trapping from nanotextured substrates follows mainly Yablonovitch model leading to an apparent shift of absorption edge. This contrasts with micro-rough substrates and also the remarkable efficient light trapping capabilities of bare layers due to their native surface roughness, where the path enhancement in this case is almost uniform, making the layer optically thicker by factor two or more. Light scattering optical models as well as analytical techniques are reviewed and a new insights are presented.

Introduction

Hybrid organic-inorganic lead halide perovskites are a class of semiconductor thin-film material with remarkable optoelectronic properties, being currently the only wide bandgap top cell candidates for tandem devices working with crystalline silicon bottom cells exceeding 30% efficiency, as first demonstrated by researchers at EPFL/CSEM Neuchâtel [1], then further improved by other academic groups [2], until the record was finally taken over by industry company Longi with 34.6% efficient device [3]. Especially in tandem cells, where it is not possible to apply a back reflector behind the perovskite layer, uncomplete absorptance leads to transmittance of photons through the top cell, leading to overlapping components of the external quantum efficiencies of the top and bottom cells in range 600 nm – 800 nm [4,5]. Front micrometer scale textured surface considerably reduces this effect due to geometric light path enhancement as can be seen from comparison of tandems with flat and textured front surface from the same laboratory [1,6]. A similar geometrical optical path enhancement concept was successfully demonstrated by glass texturing [7]. The use of periodic nano-structuring for light trapping was studied extensively theoretically, e.g. based on pyramidal surface [8,9] inverted cones [10] or ZnO photonic crystals [11]. Experimentally, this was demonstrated e.g. by diffraction gratings, making use of CD and DVD discs [12]. Conversely, random texturing of transparent conductive oxide (TCO) substrates was experimentally demonstrated only with moderate success [13,14], mainly due to very low contrast of refractive indices [15] between TCO and perovskite layer. More successful was therefore concept of random nanotexturing of back reflector [16] where the contrast was guaranteed by interface with metal. Metal interfaces provide plasmonic effects that do increase useful absorptance [17–19], but principally also the parasitic absorptance can be increased [20]. Interface between perovskite and air also provides sufficient refractive index contrast. In early days of perovskite solar cell technology, idealized Yablonovitch limit path enhancement [21] for such a case was evaluated analytically. Yablonovitch limit represents a theoretical model [22] giving maximum path enhancement of $2n^2$ ($4n^2$ for back reflector) where n represents the layer refractive index. This factor comes from intensity enhancement in medium with higher refractive index n compared to vacuum according to $I_{int} = n^2 I_{ext}$ [22]. As we deal with local enhancement, where the reference intensity is the one of the near ambient that may not be air but glass or a liquid, we obviously have to account for its refractive index n_{amb} too. The limit can be written as follows [23]:

$$A_{Yablonovich} \cong \left[1 + \frac{1}{2\alpha(n/n_{amb})^2 d} \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where the refractive index is reduced by refractive index of ambient n_{amb} , α is absorption coefficient and d is a layer thickness. The equation (1) was derived only for the case where $\alpha d \ll 1$, however for the purposes of approximate determination of solar cell efficiency limits it is sometimes used in whole range. Another model, based on scalar scattering theory [24] and ray tracing analysis was developed for bulk and surface scattering in the case of microcrystalline silicon by Poruba [25]. Equations of Poruba model are given in Supporting Information. The main parameter of the model is the root-mean-square roughness (RMS). Finally, the simplest mathematical model of absorptance enhancement due to light trapping is to assume uniform extension of the path length by a constant δ . Then absorptance following Lambert-Beer law takes a simple form of equation (2):

$$A \cong 1 - e^{-\alpha\delta d} \quad (2)$$

Note that in all these models we do not account for multiple internal reflections for non-scattered portion of light. The goal is to evaluate potential of random roughness scattering and different scattering models from the point of insufficient absorptance in lead halide perovskite structures in the range from 500 nm to 800 nm.

Theory

Figure 1: Absorptance curves (the reflectance is assumed to be zero) of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ layers simulated by different analytical models for different intensity of light trapping effect.

For illustration, the above mentioned models were theoretically compared in Figure 1. As the model perovskite material we chose the most basic methylammonium lead iodide $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ (MAPI). Optical constants of this material were determined from optical measurement of layer prepared on glass substrate. For the details of material preparation and optical properties determination refer to Supporting Information. The simulated thickness was 500 nm. This represents the baseline case (single pass). In all the cases the loss from reflectance was neglected. For different models we focused on the absorptance from 1.5 eV to 2.2 eV. Below the bandgap we observe (x-axis is stretched here) the apparent absorption edge shift and above the bandgap we observe the increase in amount of absorbed photons. It can be seen that obviously the best absorption enhancement is achieved by extending (e.g.

doubling) the photon path length (double pass, $\delta = 2$), which is equivalent to implementing some strong geometrical light trapping/management (e.g. back reflector). Effect of Yablonovitch limit is gradually “switched on” from 5% to 100% by making a weighted average between the single pass and Yablonovitch limit. This represents the assumption that only part of the photons is scattered. Yablonovitch limit has the strongest effect on the apparent absorption edge shift. Compared to uniform photon path enhancement Yablonovitch limit does not reach full absorption above bandgap. Poruba model is scaling with the value of RMS and is quite similar with uniform photon path enhancement, but the absorption enhancement is limited to maximum path length of approximately $\delta \leq 3$. Poruba model also produces small apparent shift in absorption edge. Apart from that Poruba model gives very similar spectra as uniform path enhancement. Interestingly, if we try to relate by the simulations the path enhancement δ to RMS roughness in Poruba model, we obtain different trends for different layer thicknesses, see inset of Figure 2. To evaluate the effect on solar cell performance, the absorptance multiplied by solar radiation AM1.5G spectrum was integrated and relative photogeneration enhancement factors were evaluated, see graphical interpretation in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of relative photogeneration increases for different types of light trapping models for $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ layer with 500 nm thickness. The inset shows approximate relation between Poruba model and uniform path enhancement.

We see that doubling the light path in 500 nm thick layer of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ results in more than 16% relative efficiency increase, tripling leads to 22% increase, which is almost as good as maximum of Yablonovitch and Poruba model that can both increase the photocurrent up to 22% and 23%, respectively.

Results

Native perovskite surface roughness

If we want to evaluate the absorptance enhancement, we have to know absorption coefficient and refractive index of a single layer on glass (Figure S2 in Supporting Information). We therefore start with layers on glass. We prepared a set of 9 different layers of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ on glass with varying thickness and varying crystallinity, in order to control surface roughness. The thickness categories were 160 nm, 250 nm, and 500 nm and the grain size categories are S, M, L as small/medium/large. For varying crystallinity, the previously developed recipe was used [26]. For further details of preparation, refer to Supporting Information. Absorptance was then evaluated by measurement of Photothermal Deflection Spectroscopy (PDS). This measurement was performed in a liquid with refractive index $n_{liquid} = 1.25$, which is close to 1, and does not considerably reduce the surface scattering compared to the case of air. In the models, however, this detail is considered. For accurate comparison between the models and the samples that exhibited a slight variation in the thicknesses, the interference fringes were first removed by dividing the measured absorptance by $(1 - R)$ [27] and the thickness variation was corrected by running Lambert-Beer law back and forth to match the thickness of the respective category. The thicknesses were measured by cross-sectional SEM. For more details refer to Supporting Information. We tried to reproduce the behavior by simplest models and we saw that already the model of uniform path length enhancement ($\delta > 1$) reproduced sufficiently well all the experimental curves, see Figure 3. Remarkably, the values of uniform path length enhancements up to $\delta = 2.7$ were observed. Obviously, the question is how the true value of absorption coefficient can be determined. We simply took the lowest value that we could observe – in the case of sample L500 – the only one yielding the path length enhancement of $\delta = 1$.

Figure 3: Absorptance of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ layers on glass measured by PDS and recalculated to the same thicknesses (labeled as d_{ref}), fitted by model (dashed line) with uniform path length enhancement (values of path length δ are given in brackets together with RMS roughness in nm).

For proving the absorptance enhancement independently from any simulations we measured also photocurrent spectrum between the two electrodes by Fourier-Transform Photocurrent Spectroscopy (FTPS), from layer side and from glass side. For more details, refer to Supporting Information. It is well known from the photocurrent methodology, that the size of the actual illumination and detection area have to be taken into account. The scattered light in the spectral region around 1.5 eV, where the absorption coefficients is around 100 cm^{-1} has a penetration length of around 0.1 mm and can therefore travel parallel to the substrate. Like this, the illumination of the layer through the gap between the electrodes will give different results compared to the situation when much larger area is illuminated from the glass side. The effect is schematically sketched in Figure S4. These effect of illumination and electrode geometry on the signal enhancement in low absorptance region were described extensively in relation to light trapping in thin films of microcrystalline silicon [25,28]. In Figure 4 we compare FTPS spectra measured by illumination from layer side (through the electrode gap) and by illumination from the glass side. In the graph the ratio of the two curves is also shown, indicating enhancements of around 30%. The value is only approximate as the two spectra are normalized to each other at 1.7 eV. The purpose of this test is just to proof existence of any absorption enhancement due to light trapping.

Figure 4: Simple proof of the light trapping by the observed difference between FTPS spectra measured by illumination from the glass side and a layer side (through the gap in the electrodes) for randomly chosen samples.

The effect of light trapping requires scattering either from some bulk features or from the surface. The light trapping enhancement δ can be compared to RMS values obtained from atomic force microscopy (AFM), see Figure S6 in the Supporting Information. RMS values and δ values are given in the legend of Figure 3. We see, however, that the correlation is not very good in this case. This means that the RMS as a single number is not a sufficient parameter for describing light scattering effect. To find a better correlation, the angular distribution function (ADF) of the scattered light in the reflection mode from layer side was measured with red laser, see Figure 5. Although scattering in reality happens on the internal surface while we can experimentally assess this only on the external surface, ADF can still serve for a relative comparison. In principle the relation of internal and external ADF is possible using existing scattering models [15]. The ADF functions were normalized to the laser intensity. Refer to Supporting Information for further measurement details. The light scattering from the surface is increasing from sample L160 (lowest) to M500 (highest). Comparing with path length enhancement we see that M160 has highest δ value which is

has the highest ADF curve among samples in 160 nm thickness category. On the other hand, the lowest δ is found for L500 that has lowest ADF in the 500 nm thickness category. This means that not only ADF values, but the thickness has an effect on light trapping enhancement. The likely explanation is the higher number of scattering events encountered in thinner samples.

Figure 5: Angular Distribution Function of scattered light from $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ layers on glass measured in reflectance mode by red laser.

Nano-rough and micro-rough substrates

While the native perovskite surface roughness in contact with air may exhibit remarkable absorptance enhancement, the effect of interface with substrate might be more important practically. Therefore we test the perovskite layers prepared on nano-rough TCO substrates and on micro-rough glass substrates. Motivated by thin-film silicon technology [29,30] we first deposited various layers of ZnO by radiofrequency sputtering with varying power density leading to varying surface roughness (samples ZnO A, ZnO B, and ZnO C). The third sample (FTO) was a commercial $\text{SnO}_2:\text{F}$ U-type layer from Asahi Glass Company [19,31]. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images are provided in Supporting Information. To increase the refractive index contrast, the layer of gold (100 nm) was coated on the top of the surfaces, mimicking the surface texturing of back reflector [16]. Perovskite layers were then deposited by spin coating on TCO and on glass for reference. Details about the layer preparation are provided in Supporting Information. To avoid instability issues linked to methylammonium or mixed halide perovskites the material of choice for experiments with different roughness was $\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{CS}_{0.1}\text{PbI}_3$. These layers were stable when deposited on TCO substrates. From the cross-sectional SEM images (inset of Figure S6) we can see that the roughness of the substrate had a negligible effect on the surface roughness of the perovskite layer. We measured the absorptance by PDS. The measurement was performed in a range where the absorptance in perovskite dominated over the absorptance in TCO or gold that can be revealed due to its almost constant absorptance contrasting with sharp absorption edge of perovskite. Spectra were corrected again by dividing by $(1 - R)$. We tried to interpret the simulated curves in the framework of simple models and we found that a combination of uniform path enhancement ($\delta > 1$) with Yablonovitch model is reproducing the results with

good approximation, see Figure 6. Note that for a layer on a (thick) glass measured by PDS the term $(n_{amb})^2$ is set to $n_{glass}n_{liquid}$ to account for the refractive index of the glass and the liquid. In the case of gold layer the factor 2 in the Yablonoitch limit is replaced by 4 and $(n_{amb})^2$ is set to $(n_{liquid})^2$. Interestingly, unlike the native surface roughness, for these nano-rough TCOs Yablonoitch model is always necessary and in the case of FTO and gold coating the pure Yablonoitch limit is achieved. The parameters are summarized in Table 1. The light trapping enhancement also correlates with the ADF functions shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Absorbance of $\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{Cs}_{0.1}\text{PbI}_3$ layers on top of TCO measured by PDS (without correction to varying thickness). Inset shows the cross-sectional SEM images (white scale bar represents 1 μm).

Figure 7: Angular Distribution Function of scattered light from nano-rough ITO layers with and without gold coating, measured by red laser.

In parallel with the nano-roughness obtained by textured TCO, we investigated also a micro-rough surfaces of glass prepared by very simple mechanical methods. Corning microscopic slides CLS294775X50 were used in different treatments, named as glass 0, A, B and F. Glass 0 is without any treatment, glass A and glass B were grinded by sandpaper with density 2000 and 1200 respectively and glass F is the blasted (frosted) area of the microscope slide. Resulting PDS spectra are in the Figure 8. From the SEM images (inset of Figure 8) we see that the perovskite layer cannot conformally coat glass F substrate and the thickness therefore does not have a physical meaning. For the calculations, however, we assumed a value of 500 nm. We again reproduced the results by the combination of uniform path enhancement ($\delta > 1$) with Yablonoitch model. For glasses without gold coating, except the glass F, the effect small ($\delta \leq 1.2$) path enhancement alone describe the light trapping effect. For glass F and the use of gold coating, the Yablonoitch model must be included, but never fully as in the case of nano-rough surfaces. The parameters are summarized in the Table 1. The light trapping enhancement also correlates with the ADF functions shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8: Absorbance of $\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{Cs}_{0.1}\text{PbI}_3$ layers on top of glass substrates with different roughness, measured by PDS and corrected to the thickness variations. The inset shows the cross-sectional SEM images (white scale bar represents $1 \mu\text{m}$, in the case of glass F the perovskite layer is highlighted by green color).

Figure 9: Angular Distribution Function of scattered light from micro-rough glass substrates with and without gold coating, measured by red laser.

Table 1: Model fit parameters.

sample	bare			with gold coating		
	RMS (nm)	enhance- ment δ	Yabl. contrib.	RMS (nm)	enhance- ment δ	Yabl. contrib.
ZnO A	26 ± 6	1	10 %	26 ± 6	1.3	55 %
ZnO B	34 ± 10	1	15 %	32 ± 9	1.2	80 %
ZnO C	50 ± 17	1	25 %	61 ± 17	1.2	70 %
FTO	173 ± 42	1.15	36 %	150 ± 50	---	100 %
glass 0	8 ± 2	1	---	10 ± 2	1.4	50 %
glass A	112 ± 21	1.05	---	266 ± 53	1.3	70 %
glass B	80 ± 21	1.2	---	57 ± 13	1.4	60 %
glass F	220 ± 110	1.6	50 %	500 ± 100	1.4	80 %

Conclusions

In conclusion, this work studies the role of random texture scattering in enhancing absorptance particularly between 500 nm and 800 nm in hybrid halide perovskite layers. Our findings reveal that nano-rough textured substrates offer limited gains due to low refractive index contrast. This can be overcome by introducing metal (Au) coating that considerably improves the light trapping tending to follow Yablonovitch limit, enhancing mainly medium

absorbing photons. Micro-rough substrates, produced by mechanical treatment of glass, led to enhancement that is more tending to uniform optical thickness enhancement. In contrast with that is the native surface roughness of perovskite layers in air which behavior follows uniform optical thickness completely, effectively extending the optical path length several times. Experimentally, this can be revealed by comparing photocurrent spectroscopy between coplanar contacts, measured from film and substrate side. The uniform optical thickness enhancement is a good approximation to a much-sophisticated Poruba model that is based on scalar scattering theory and in agreement with this model the optical path enhancement is stronger in thinner layers. Scalar scattering theory, taking RMS roughness as a parameter, represents a good base for modelling light trapping in solar cells as well as for evaluation of optical constants, however RMS parameter does not correlate to the one obtained from AFM measurements. This work highlights the importance of light trapping enhancement in the perspective of potential in improving perovskite photovoltaic devices.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the support of Czech Science Foundation through the project no. 23-06285S, Czech Technical University in Prague student grant SGS24/135/OHK3/3T/13, and the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

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